

REHABILITATION AFTER CAESAREAN SECTION

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Research relevance: CS entered the practice of obstetrics in 1916 as a last resort for childbirth. This made it possible to reduce the death of women and complications for newborns that may occur during childbirth. But the death rate after caesarean section was 4-8 times higher than after natural birth. Since the 1970s, the popularity of the operation has increased and its indications have expanded.

Today, the world is facing a situation where CS is done more and more often. The frequency of CS in Ukraine is constantly increasing - from 9.58% in 1999 to 16.10% in 2009, and now it is 18-25% of the total number of births, which reflects the global growth trend of this indicator makes 1 .

Materials needed: Today, CS is one of the most common low-risk surgeries.

During the intervention, an incision is made in the woman's uterus and the baby is taken out. Over the past decades, the operation itself has changed significantly 3 :

the woman is conscious due to spinal and epidural anesthesia;

the mother can immediately hold the baby in her arms, early breastfeeding is used in maternity hospitals;

The father may be present in the delivery room to provide immediate access and skin-to-skin contact with the baby.

But after CS there is a long recovery period that you have to deal with.

Novonarozhena cuts off the baby's finger

Rehabilitation after caesarean section

Observed results: If the caesarean section was successfully performed, the postoperative period can be divided into several periods.

The first day

The woman spends the first hours after the operation in the intensive care unit. After the end of the anesthesia in the operation, the woman is offered painkillers. Urinary catheter is removed no later than 12 hours after the operation. On the first day after cesarean section, there is severe pain, it is difficult for a woman to get out of bed independently.

Breastfeeding after cesarean is possible immediately when the baby is given to the mother and they come to the ward together. But milk can be delayed - from 3 to 7 days 2 .

The first weeks

After cesarean delivery, the recovery of the uterus occurs more slowly than after the natural birth of the baby. In order for the organ to fully restore its functions, a scar must appear. In the first weeks, a woman will have a discharge called lochia. They consist of bloody discharge, mucus and dying uterine epithelium. Lochia after cesarean section may be more rare than after natural birth. On average, they last 4-6 weeks.

What not to do after cesarean before your first visit to the gynecologist:

having sex;

performing sports exercises;

visit the sauna and bath, take a bath;

lifting weights.

The healing process of the suture occurs gradually, but after 5-10 days, doctors remove the sutures (if self-absorbing materials are not used).

Long-term recovery 2

How long it takes to recover after a cesarean section depends on the woman's body and how the operation went. In general, after 1-2 weeks, the young mother feels better, if there are no complications.

After discharge, you should come to the gynecologist for a regular check-up. That is, in 4-8 weeks. The woman undergoes a control ultrasound and examination in the chair.

The gynecologist also answers the question of how long it is possible to make love after giving birth.

If the state of the uterus is normal, the doctor "gives permission" for physical training and sex, as well as advice on contraceptive methods. Repeated pregnancy after surgery and birth of a baby through natural childbirth is not recommended before 2 years due to the high risk of complications.

Also, don't forget to wear a special bandage after cesarean section. It is necessary in the first weeks after the operation. The bandage tightens the abdomen and stimulates the release of lochia. Helps a woman move independently: wearing a brace makes it easier to get out of bed, lie on it, and change positions. Without it, the pain may be more pronounced.

Conclusion: One of the first questions that women are interested in: how long will the stitches last after cesarean section? A scar appears in the first days after the operation, so the

stitches are removed on the 5th day. Until then, the seam is treated with antiseptic solutions. Your gynecologist should explain how to apply sutures after a cesarean section. Usually it is tincture of iodine or calendula. After the sutures are removed, the suture can be moistened.

Further recovery of the uterus and scar formation occurs more slowly. A caesarean scar may itch and the area around it may feel "stingy." This is a normal phenomenon during rehabilitation.

What can you eat after cesarean section?

On the first day after the operation, it is recommended to drink a lot of liquid and eat soft foods - cereals, soups. In the future, eating after cesarean section will become normal. Do not forget that if the mother is breastfeeding, the diet after cesarean section is equivalent to the diet of a nursing mother. Now it is important to include foods rich in vitamins and minerals in your diet.

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